

CASE DESCRIPTIONS

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL TO THE MANUSCRIPT

Assessing the credibility of quantitative information: a general framework

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1. Measurement - Credibility of strain gauge measurements

The Context of Use (CoU) is that of measurements of bone tissue deformation to validate a finite element model to predict bone fracture. The experimental protocol used to apply the sensors to the bone tissue, their calibration, and all details on the measurement chain can be found here (Viceconti et al., 1992). The error threshold is defined considering that cortical bone yields in compression at $7300 \mu\epsilon$ and that the fracture/no fracture decision occurs in a region of strain values that is approximately 20% of this value. So, the finite element model should have an accuracy in predicting strain at least one order of magnitude higher than that, and conversely, the strain measurements used to validate it should have an accuracy of two orders of magnitude higher than that. Thus, the error threshold for this CoU is $14.6 \mu\epsilon$ (S1).

Since strain gauges are extremely accurate, finding another sensor that can serve as a true value is challenging. Typically, their validation is performed by creating a condition where the deformation is known and using that as the true value. In this case, slender beams of aluminium alloy with a rectangular cross-section are produced from a thicker block of material using Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machining with very tight tolerances. Aluminium alloy is chosen because, among linear elastic isotropic materials, it has a modulus of elasticity closer to human bone. The block is clamped, and the other extremity is loaded with a known imposed displacement. The imposed displacement is chosen as the one that maximises reproducibility between repeated experiments. The strain gauge is located at mid-length on the maximum tensile side of the beam to minimise border effects. A twin strain gauge is placed on the undeformed region of the block to compensate for thermal drifts. Calculations based on the beams’ theory corrected for curvature error provide the true value. More information on this type of validation experiment is provided in an HBM note¹ (S2).

We conducted the study on five specimens, performing ten loading repetitions per specimen, and calculated the measurement error for each. We confirmed that the error does not correlate with the specimen number (suggesting machining errors) or the repetition number (suggesting some post-elastic residuals). We calculated the trueness of the measurement as the root mean square error (S3).

Measurements are affected by systematic and aleatoric errors. We confirm that the errors are normally distributed using a normality test, with a mean value close to zero (S4-S6).

The same experiment is repeated with slender rectangular cortical bone specimens machined from the diaphysis of a bovine femur, with the beam aligned in the predominant direction of

¹ <https://www.hbkworld.com/en/knowledge/resource-center/articles/strain-measurement-basics/strain-gauge-fundamentals/measurement-uncertainty-experimental-stress-analysis>

the osteons. We use bovine cortical bone because its high degree of mineralisation makes it more homogenous than human bone. A twin gauge is glued on the remaining diaphysis to compensate for thermal drift. Experiments are conducted with specimens wrapped in wet gauze to preserve bone humidity. Therefore, before starting the experiments, all gauges must be tested for electrical isolation. We add a second strain gauge on the maximum compression side of the beam and validate both, since bone yields at a lower strain in compression than in tension. Compared to the aluminium alloy, the elasticity modulus of these specimens is unknown. Therefore, all true value and measurement error calculations are normalised for the elasticity module, using a conventional value of 20 GPa. If the errors are comparable to the ones found with the aluminium specimens, we can assume sufficient applicability (S7).

2. Biophysical prediction - Credibility of CT-based prediction of human bone deformation

The CoU is to predict the mechanical strains induced in a subject's bone under a given loading when a properly calibrated Computed Tomography (CT) of the bone is provided. The error threshold is defined considering that cortical bone yields in compression at $7300 \mu\epsilon$ and that the fracture/no fracture decision occurs in a region of strain values that is approximately 20% of this value. So, the finite element model should have an accuracy in predicting strain at least one order of magnitude higher than that. Thus, the error threshold for this CoU is $146 \mu\epsilon$ (S1).

The source of true value lies in the strain gauge measurements we perform on properly preserved human cadaver femurs, which retain their mechanical properties (Ohman et al., 2008). The specimen is CT-scanned using a protocol that maximises the accuracy in reconstructing the bone anatomy (Lattanzi et al., 2004), and the scan is properly calibrated (Schileo et al., 2008a). Bones are instrumented with 13 rosette strain gauges (Taddei et al., 2006). The bones are loaded to simulate a single-leg stance (Schileo et al., 2007) or a side fall (Grassi et al., 2012). Various 3D coordinates of the experimental setup (location of gauges, constraint level, load application points, bone surface) are collected with a digitiser to allow the spatial registration of the experiment to the model (Schileo et al., 2007). Ramp loading confirms the linearity between imposed loading and measured strains (S2).

The CT-scan data are processed into a heterogeneous finite element model of the cadaver bone. Digitiser data are used to align the experiment's model and define the exact location of the strain gauges on the bone, as well as the direction of the boundary conditions. The loading intensity is measured with the load cell of the testing machine used in the validation experiment. Strain gauge locations are imposed as hard points to the automatic mesh generation algorithm so that a finite element node always corresponds to the centre of each strain gauge. Nodal interpolation of the principal strains is used to obtain the closest prediction to the superficial strain measured by the gauges. The prediction error is calculated by comparing the predicted superficial principal strains to the values measured by the rosette strain gauges for each bone, loading condition, and strain gauge location (Schileo et al., 2007; Grassi et al., 2012).

The credibility assessment can be conducted in accordance with the ASME VV40:2018 technical standard, which applies to biophysical models (Aldieri et al., 2023). The predictions of biophysical models are affected by numerical, aleatoric and epistemic errors; the verification, validation and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) procedure separates them (Viceconti et al., 2020) (S4-S5). In all cases, prediction errors are expected not to exceed the acceptability threshold. The numerical error component must be negligible compared to the other two; the aleatoric component must be normally distributed with a mean close to zero, and the epistemic component should have a root mean square error close to zero (S6).

. Applicability analysis, in this case, is done by brute force. Experiments are designed to explore inter-subject variability and all possible loading conditions, the two primary sources of bias (Schileo et al., 2008a; Grassi et al., 2012) (S7).

3. Biophysical prediction - Credibility of CT-based prediction of human bone strength

The CoU is to predict the intensity of the minimum force required to fracture a subject's bone under a given loading when a properly calibrated CT of the bone is provided. Considering the model predicts the strength using a strain-based failure criterion, and the RMS average error on the strain prediction is $83 \mu\epsilon$, which is 8% of the ultimate strain in tension, and considering the initiation of fracture in a bone is influenced by porosities smaller than the resolution of the whole bone model, we can assume the error threshold for this CoU is at least twice that on the strain, so 16% of the measured value (S1).

The controlled experiment used to produce the true value is the same as that used to validate the strain predictions. Cadaver bones are CT-scanned and then loaded to failure using different loading directions, and the force that initiates the crack propagation is taken as the true strength value. The load cell used to measure the force experimentally has a trueness of $\pm 0.5\%$ of the measured value, which is sufficient to validate the model. Under side-fall loading, the proximal fracture propagates in human femurs in a few milliseconds, so there is no ambiguity about the force to be assumed as the true value: it is the maximum force measured by the load cell (S2).

The prediction error is calculated as the standard error of the estimate (SEE) between the measured and predicted strengths over some experiments with different femurs and loading directions. Because the model assumes a linear relationship between load intensity and strain intensity (justified by the fragile failure observed experimentally), for each femur and loading condition, the strength is predicted by simulating a conventional loading value, predicting the location and value of maximum tensile and compressive principal strains, and then extrapolate the force intensity required to increase those strains to the respective ultimate values (10,400 $\mu\epsilon$ in tension, 7,300 $\mu\epsilon$ in compression) (Schileo et al., 2008a)(S3).

Regarding the strain prediction case, the predictions of biophysical models are affected by numerical, aleatoric, and epistemic errors. The verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) procedure separates these errors (Viceconti et al., 2020) (S4-S5). In all cases, prediction errors are expected not to exceed the acceptability threshold. The numerical error component must be negligible compared to the other two; the aleatoric component must be normally distributed with a mean close to zero, and the epistemic component should have a root mean square error close to zero (Aldieri et al., 2023) (S6).

The main issue, in this case, is that while for the strain prediction, a single cadaver bone can provide a large number of measured validation values (13 strain gauges, two principal strains each, multiple loading directions, multiple repetitions per direction), here, since the experiment irreversibly damages the specimen, each cadaver femur yields only one validation value. Thus, applicability cannot be demonstrated by brute force. In addition, bone fracture is influenced by several subject-specific and environmental factors that are beyond the control of the experiment. To address this, the applicability analysis can be done by comparing the average prediction error found in the experimental study with the errors reported by other authors in similar studies on similar modelling techniques, once the errors are normalised to the same representation, for example, the SEE (Viceconti et al., 2018) (S7).

4. Biophysical prediction - Credibility of CT-based prediction of risk of hip fracture

The CoU is to predict the Absolute Risk of Fracture at the current time (ARF0) of the proximal femur upon falling for a subject when a properly calibrated CT of the bone is provided. Here, given the clinical use of the predictor, the error threshold must be decided based on clinical usefulness considerations. Considering the stratification error for the current standard of care (DXA-measured total hip areal bone mineral density, DXA-aBMD), the literature reports classification accuracy ranging from 65% to 75%. To be adopted in clinical practice, a new method must improve the current one by at least 10%, so the acceptability threshold over stratification error is 20% (80% accuracy) (S1).

Two experimental designs can be used for validation. A longitudinal observational design would involve recruiting and following up a large number of fragile elders over several years. This is because hip fractures are relatively rare events, even in populations at relatively high risk. For example, in a cohort of 1528 women with a mean (SD) age of 84.1 (3.4) years, during the five-year follow-up, only 125 (8.0%) experienced a hip fracture (Ensrud et al., 2019). Such an observational study would require some thousand patients enrolled for five years to be sufficiently powered; the alternative is a cross-sectional pair-matched clinical study, where patients who just had a hip fracture and CT-scan their contralateral femur are recruited together with pair-matched patients of the same age, gender, height, and weight who did not have a hip fracture (e.g., (Yang et al., 2014)) (S2).

These studies always use the DXA-aBMD as a comparator. With the first study design, the ARF0 predicted from a CT scan performed at the outset would be compared to the DXA-aBMD value measured simultaneously by correlating them with the time without fracture observed experimentally for each patient. In the second study design, we would compare the stratification accuracy of ARF0 and DXA-aBMD calculated as the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) (S3).

The credibility of such a predictor can be explored following the VVUQ approach for biophysical models proposed in the ASME VV40:2018 technical standard (Aldieri et al., 2023) (S4-S7). This credibility analysis would probably be considered sufficient for certifying this predictor in the class predictive software as a medical device. However, in qualification advice with the European Medicines Agency (EMA), where such a predictor, called BBCT-Hip, was proposed as a surrogate biomarker of the primary endpoint proximal femoral fracture in phase II clinical trials to evaluate the efficacy of a new antiresorptive drug, this level of credibility evidence was considered insufficient (Viceconti et al., 2024a). EMA recommended that, at most, the predictive model could be considered in a much more limited context of use (surrogate biomarker of the primary endpoint, proximal femoral fracture in multi-dose Phase II studies to evaluate the efficacy of new antiresorptive treatments). In addition, the cross-sectional pair-matched design was considered insufficient to demonstrate credibility, and a longitudinal observational design was requested. This regulatory position is extensively discussed in (Viceconti et al., 2024b).

5. Synthetic dataset – Virtual cohort for In Silico Trials of interventions to prevent hip fractures

In hip fracture, biophysical predictors such as BBCT-Hip are used to represent each patient, who is characterised by a feature set that serves as input for the model. This feature set includes the femoral geometry and bone mineral density distribution extracted from the CT scan, as well as the patient's height and weight. A cross-sectional pair-matched clinical study used to validate a predictor typically enrolls 100 patients, whereas a randomised interventional clinical trial to assess the efficacy of treatment against a placebo or a comparator generally requires at least

1000 patients per arm. One possible solution is the generation of a virtual cohort, defined as a collection of synthetically generated feature sets that represent a larger cohort, statistically equivalent in terms of its properties.

For the purpose at hand, a patient is represented by a set of values (feature set) that can be measured experimentally on that patient and are necessary and sufficient to accurately predict another quantity of interest that cannot be easily measured. A *Clinical Cohort* is a group of patients selected according to specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. This selection defines a sub-population of which this patient group is a sample. A *Virtual Cohort* is a collection of feature sets measured on the patients of the clinical cohort. A synthetic cohort is a virtual cohort obtained by inferring the feature set values of other patients who belong to the same sub-population of the clinical cohort. A key issue in this case is the dimensionality of the features. Suppose all the features in the set have a dimensionality low enough that it is possible to define a “similarity metric” between two instances of that feature. In that case, we can utilise methods such as Principal Component Analysis to reduce further dimensionality (La Mattina et al., 2023). However, for higher-dimensional features (e.g., medical imaging datasets), more sophisticated methods, such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) (Pesaranghader et al., 2021), are required. Here, we will consider only the first case, where such a similarity metric can be defined.

The context of use we are considering is to use, in place of an experimentally collected virtual cohort, a synthetic cohort of feature sets of the BBCT-Hip predictor to evaluate *in silico* the efficacy of different interventions aimed at reducing the risk of hip fracture in fragile elderly, on a much larger virtual cohort than would be practically possible using only experimental data. In this CoU, we plan to compare specific central properties of two probability distributions (mean and median), so the error should be expressed in terms of the maximum acceptable difference for these properties. This should apply to both distributions of values for each feature in the set and for the model's predictions when such values are provided as inputs. In terms of error threshold, the difference in the median values for each feature between the virtual cohort and the synthetic cohort, as well as those of the average quantity of interest predicted by the model between the virtual and synthetic cohorts, should never exceed the accuracy with which each of those quantities is measured or predicted (S1).

The source of true values is the virtual cohort, the set of feature set values measured experimentally on the subjects forming the clinical cohort (S2).

Of course, no one-to-one comparison is possible; we can only compare the distribution of values observed in the virtual and synthetic cohorts for each feature. So, the estimation error is defined for each feature as the difference between the median values of the two distributions (S3).

Synthetic datasets are generated through inference from experimental data, thereby eliminating any epistemic error. The aleatoric error is due to the uncertainty of the experimental measurements. The numerical errors are those produced for each feature by the interpolation function that generates new synthetic values (S4).

The aleatoric error can be estimated by conducting a sensitivity analysis on how the measurement errors affecting the feature values in the virtual cohort propagate in values inferred for the synthetic cohort. We can calculate such sensitivity by perturbing the values of the virtual cohort following the uncertainty distribution of the measurement chain used to quantify them and regenerating the synthetic cohort. Once the aleatoric error is defined, we need to verify that the numerical error of the interpolators is negligible in comparison to it. The method for doing this depends on the type of interpolating function used for each feature. For PCA, one possibility is to recalculate the synthetic cohort excluding the least significant

component and observe the differences this causes. This approach overestimates the numerical error, but if it is small enough, the verification condition is satisfied (S5, S6).

The applicability analysis of information produced by inference is simple: the resulting information can be used only in cases that fall in the portion of the information space defined by the feature set sampled in the virtual cohort. Therefore, if feature F is assumed in the clinical cohort values between F1 and F2, only synthetic values with F in the range F1 to F2 should be considered at full credibility. Any extrapolation outside the limits of the original information space has lower credibility; the farther from those limits, the lower the credibility (S7).

6. In Silico Trial - Credibility of a model to predict interventions' efficacy on a clinical cohort

The BoneStrength In Silico Trial combines the BBCT-Hip digital twin of a synthetic cohort, a model of disease progression over the sub-population of interest, and a model of the intervention's mechanism of action, aiming to predict its efficacy. Because the propensity to fall, the progression of the disease (bone loss), and the action of the intervention are formulated as stochastic predictors, the BoneStrength In Silico Trial utilises a Markov-Chain Monte Carlo method to explore the adjoint probability space that these stochastic inputs produce. Each time the In Silico Trial is repeated, it will yield a different result. Still, with enough repetitions, we can see the mean and variance of the predicted quantity of interest converge asymptotically. As a prediction of the model, we calculate the range of the number of hip fractures predicted across repetitions, both with and without the effect of the intervention simulated.

The Context of Use of BoneStrength is to predict the outcome of randomised clinical trials aimed to assess the efficacy of an intervention (whose mechanism of action is known), so to use this information to inform the design of such trials or to reduce the number of patients enrolled by using an in-silico-augmented adaptive Bayesian design of the clinical trial (Haddad et al., 2017). In the validation studies, we compare a distribution of possible predicted values (estimated with a finite number of replications of the In Silico Trial) with a single value observed experimentally, using a one-sample t-test for a single observation. Given the number of degrees of freedom (patients in the virtual cohort minus one), a t-value corresponds to a probability value that that single experimental observation is part of the population simulated by the model. Thus, we can assume the t-value as error metrics and a corresponding probability $p < 0.05$ as the acceptability threshold. A confidence interval of 5% is typical in clinical decision-making (Miller and Ulrich, 2019) (S1).

In this case, the true value can be provided by interventional randomised clinical trials designed to assess the efficacy of a specific intervention on the number of hip fractures observed over some time, typically three to five years (S2).

In this case, the estimation error is a prediction error, but in the context of an L2 validation (Viceconti et al., 2021), which means distance from a median value for the population. Thus, we can use the t-value to measure the distance (error) between the number of fractures observed in the clinical trial and the average value of the number of fractures predicted in the replications (S3).

At the heart of BoneStrength, there is a biophysical predictor that is affected by numeric, aleatoric, and epistemic errors. But BoneStrength is an orchestration of multiple models: a stochastic biophysical model to predict the impact force upon falling; the BBCT biophysical model to predict if such fall causes fracture; the disease progression stochastic data-driven model which predicts how the bone mineral density is reduced over time due; and the stochastic

data-driven (or knowledge-driven, depending on the case) model to simulate the effect of the intervention whose efficacy is being assessed. Following the same logic used for multiscale models (Bhattacharya et al., 2021), the error decomposition should be performed first for each component model and then again for the composite model treated as a whole (S4-S6).

In this case, the applicability analysis is limited to acknowledging that the credibility of the predictor refers to the range of feature values observed in the clinical cohort used for the validation studies. Any use of the predictor for populations with very different feature set values would result in a reduced level of credibility; again, the farther the values are from those limits, the lower the credibility (S7).

7. Surrogate model - Credibility of an ML predictor to surrogate a biophysical model

The context of use is to replace the FE component in BoneStrength with the ML surrogate to reduce the computational cost. In this regard, the definition of the acceptability threshold for the prediction error is not trivial. Since the predicted principal strain decides if that fall caused a fracture, the reference strain value is the failure strain (peak strain averaged over a sphere of 3 mm on the proximal femur surface reaches a value of 7300 $\mu\epsilon$ in the first principal strain or 10,040 $\mu\epsilon$ in the third principal strain (Schileo et al., 2008b)). Considering that the scope of the ML model is to make a more efficient computation, one would expect the error caused by such a predictor to contribute to the numerical error component of the BoneStrength predictor. As such, consistently with the classic VVUQ process, one would expect the numerical error to be one order of magnitude smaller than the overall prediction error of the model. When BBCT-Hip was validated against the experimental strain measurements on cadaver bones, it showed an average error of 6% of the maximum measured value; thus, the acceptability threshold should be 0.6% of the failure strain. However, such an error should not be computed on the quadratic norm (RMSE) but rather on the infinity norm, since we cannot accept errors greater than that threshold. Thus, the acceptability thresholds for the two principal strains are the highest error, less than 43 $\mu\epsilon$ for the tensile principal strain and 60 $\mu\epsilon$ for the compression one (S1).

Because the ML predictor surrogates the FE model, the true values against which we compute the accuracy are those predicted by the FE model. For the same reasons, we assume that all the correlated quantities C (inputs of the FE model, features of the ML predictor) are also true values, as the FE model predicts the quantity of interest by assuming the inputs to be true (S2).

If the true values were obtained experimentally, we should discuss the differences between internal (using as test set data collected in the same experimental campaign that produced the training set) and external validation (using as test set data collected in a separate experimental campaign) however, since the FE model has perfect reproducibility (with the same inputs on the same computer, the code will also predict the same output; even if we change the computer, the roundoff error differences should be minuscule), the error of the ML predictor would not change if we would compare it to additional runs of the FE model, even if obtained with a different computer. One could argue that an external validation could be obtained by changing the FE solver, but this is incorrect: the aim is to develop an ML surrogate for that FE model, including that solver. Since the abundance of true values is not an issue, instead of using advanced dataset-splitting methods such as k-fold cross-validation, we randomly split the FE model data into an equally sized training set and test set. If half of the initial dataset is insufficient for good-quality training (as measured, for example, by observing how the residuals of the training vary as the size of the training set increases), more FE simulations should be run to expand the dataset (S3).

As discussed in a recent publication (Viceconti et al., 2025), ML predictors are affected by the same types of biophysical predictor errors: numerical, aleatoric, and epistemic. The primary source of numerical error for an ML predictor is the uncertainty associated with the hyperparameters. This can be quantified by repeating the ML predictor's training many times with a 2-fold cross-validation and seeing the variability of the predictions. Such numerical error should be an order of magnitude smaller than the acceptability threshold for the context of use. (Viceconti et al., 2020). So, repeating the 2-fold cross-validation, we should observe average (RMS) differences of less than 4-6 $\mu\epsilon$. For ML-based predictors, the verification step must also include checking properties such as existence, uniqueness, smoothness, and non-chaoticity using the methods already proposed for the verification of agent-based models (Curreli et al., 2021). Again, because this is a surrogate modelling case, we assume the uncertainty affecting the correlated quantities is zero, so no uncertainty quantification in a strict sense is possible. But suppose the numerical error is confirmed to be negligible. In that case, we can assume that the standard deviation of the prediction errors on the test set is due to aleatoric uncertainty, and the average of the same prediction errors is due to epistemic uncertainty. The average error should be close to zero; if this is not the case, then there are biases that the ML predictor does not account for (S4-S6).

Again, since the ML predictor is a surrogate of an FE model, applicability analysis is a special case. Since the true values are not generated experimentally, it is quite easy to ensure that the true values used for validation cover the entire input space (for a definition, see (Viceconti et al., 2025)). Since ML predictors do not guarantee regularity properties, the verification must also include testing existence, uniqueness, smoothness, and non-chaoticity (Curreli et al., 2021). These tests require running the ML predictor over a large number of inputs chosen so that the entire input space is uniformly sampled. To do the applicability analysis in this case, we simply recommend that an additional test set be generated using these same input values (or a subsample if there are too many, as far as the statistical properties are preserved) and recalculate the prediction error over such a wide range of inputs. In addition, it is possible only in this case to calculate how the prediction error varies as a function of the inputs. Again, because this is a surrogate model, the prediction error should not be correlated with the input values (S7).

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